

‘Sort by relevance’ project: Bibliography

About this document

This is a supporting output from the project ‘Sort by relevance’: Exploring assumptions about algorithm-mediated academic literature searches’. The project was undertaken during 2022 and funded by the Society for Research in Higher Education (SRHE).

The project was focused upon the use of ranking algorithms in academic literature searches (such as Google Scholar), and sought to explore the assumptions users hold about how the algorithms work, and the implications for practice.

This document contains the bibliography from the literature search associated with the project. This is also available to download as a Bibtex file here: <http://www.katyjordan.com/srhe/biblio.bib> . For further information, the project report will be available to download from the SRHE website at: <https://srhe.ac.uk/research/completed-award-reports/> .

Acknowledgments

This research was supported by funding from the Society for Research in Higher Education (SRHE), under its annual research grants scheme. See <http://www.srhe.ac.uk> for further information.

Suggested citation

Jordan, K. & Tsai, S.P. (2023) ‘Sort by relevance’ project: *Bibliography*. Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7328625

How the Google Scholar relevance ranking algorithm works

- Beel, J., & Gipp, B. (2009). Google Scholar's ranking algorithm: An introductory overview. In: B. Larsen and J. Leta (Eds.), *Proceedings of ISSI 2009 : 12th International Conference on Scientometrics and Informetrics*, International Society for Scientometrics and Informetrics, Rio de Janeiro (Brazil), July 2009.
<https://docear.org/papers/Google%20Scholar's%20Ranking%20Algorithm%20--%20An%20Introductory%20Overview%20--%20preprint.pdf>
- Beel, J., & Gipp, B. (2009). Google Scholar's ranking algorithm: The impact of articles' age (an empirical study). *2009 Sixth International Conference on Information Technology: New Generations*, Las Vegas, NV, USA, April 2009, 160–164. doi: [10.1109/ITNG.2009.317](https://doi.org/10.1109/ITNG.2009.317)
- Beel, J. & Gipp, B. (2009) Google Scholar's ranking algorithm: The impact of citation counts (an empirical study). In: A. Flory and M. Collard (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 3rd IEEE International Conference on Research Challenges in Information Science (RCIS'09)* (Morocco), April 2009. IEEE. doi: [10.1109/RCIS.2009.5089308](https://doi.org/10.1109/RCIS.2009.5089308)
- Beel, J., Gipp, B., & Wilde, E. (2010). Academic search engine optimization (ASEO). *Journal of Scholarly Publishing*, 41(2), Article 2. doi: [10.3138/jsp.41.2.176](https://doi.org/10.3138/jsp.41.2.176)
- Ferreira, V. G., Rosa, J., Almeida, N. M., Pereira, J. S., Sabater, L. M., Vendramin, D., Zhu, H., Martens, K., & Higuti, J. (2022). A comparison of three main scientific literature databases using a search in aquatic ecology. *Hydrobiologia*. doi: [10.1007/s10750-022-05067-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-022-05067-5)
- Martin-Martin, A., Orduna-Malea, E., Harzing, A.-W., & Delgado López-Cózar, E. (2017). Can we use Google Scholar to identify highly-cited documents? *Journal of Informetrics*, 11(1), Article 1. [10.1016/j.joi.2016.11.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2016.11.008)
- Rovira, C., Codina, L., Guerrero-Solé, F., & Lopezosa, C. (2019). Ranking by relevance and citation counts, a comparative study: Google Scholar, Microsoft Academic, WoS and Scopus. *Future Internet*, 11(9), Article 9. doi: [10.3390/fi11090202](https://doi.org/10.3390/fi11090202)
- Rovira, C., Codina, L., & Lopezosa, C. (2021). Language bias in the Google Scholar ranking algorithm. *Future Internet*, 13(2), Article 2. doi: [10.3390/fi13020031](https://doi.org/10.3390/fi13020031)
- Rovira, C., Guerrero-Solé, F., & Codina, L. (2018). Received citations as a main SEO factor of Google Scholar results ranking. *El Profesional de La Información*, 27(3), Article 3. doi: [10.3145/epi.2018.may.09](https://doi.org/10.3145/epi.2018.may.09)
- Yu, K., Mustapha, N., Oozeer, N., Yu, K., Mustapha, N., & Oozeer, N. (2017). Google Scholar's filter bubble: An inflated actuality? In *Esposito, A. (Ed.) Research 2.0 and the impact of digital technologies on scholarly inquiry*. IGI Global, pp. 211-229.
<https://www.igi-global.com/gateway/chapter/www.igi-global.com/gateway/chapter/167444>

Suitability of Google Scholar for systematic reviews

- Bates, J., Best, P., McQuilkin, J., & Taylor, B. (2017). Will web search engines replace bibliographic databases in the systematic identification of research? *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 43(1), 8–17. doi: [10.1016/j.acalib.2016.11.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2016.11.003)
- Boeker, M., Vach, W., & Motschall, E. (2013). Google Scholar as replacement for systematic literature searches: Good relative recall and precision are not enough. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 13(1), 131. doi: [10.1186/1471-2288-13-131](https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-13-131)
- Gehanno, J.-F., Rollin, L., & Darmoni, S. (2013). Is the coverage of google scholar enough to be used alone for systematic reviews. *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making*, 13(1), 7. doi: [10.1186/1472-6947-13-7](https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6947-13-7)
- Giustini, D., & Boulos, M. N. K. (2013). Google Scholar is not enough to be used alone for systematic reviews. *Online Journal of Public Health Informatics*, 5(2), Article 2. doi: [10.5210/ojphi.v5i2.4623](https://doi.org/10.5210/ojphi.v5i2.4623)
- Gusenbauer, M., & Haddaway, N. R. (2020). Which academic search systems are suitable for systematic reviews or meta-analyses? Evaluating retrieval qualities of Google Scholar, PubMed, and 26 other resources. *Research Synthesis Methods*, 11(2), 181–217. doi: [10.1002/jrsm.1378](https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1378)
- Halevi, G., Moed, H., & Bar-Ilan, J. (2017). Suitability of Google Scholar as a source of scientific information and as a source of data for scientific evaluation—Review of the literature. *Journal of Informetrics*, 11(3), 823–834. doi: [10.1016/j.joi.2017.06.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2017.06.005)
- Vine, R. (2006). Google scholar. *Journal of the Medical Library Association*, 94(1), 97-99. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1324783/>

Google Scholar in the wider online scholarly ecosystem

- Goldenfein, J., & Griffin, D. (2022). Google Scholar – Platforming the scholarly economy. *Internet Policy Review*, 11(3). doi: [10.14763/2022.3.1671](https://doi.org/10.14763/2022.3.1671)
- Komljenovic, J. (2019). Big data and new social relations in higher education: Academia.edu, Google Scholar and ResearchGate. In *World Yearbook of Education 2019: Comparative Methodology in an Era of Big Data and Global Networks* (pp. 148–164). Routledge. [https://www.research.lancs.ac.uk/portal/en/publications/big-data-and-new-social-relations-in-higher-education\(37ad511b-3d48-40b3-8519-b7109cbb32df\).html](https://www.research.lancs.ac.uk/portal/en/publications/big-data-and-new-social-relations-in-higher-education(37ad511b-3d48-40b3-8519-b7109cbb32df).html)
- López-Cózar, E. D., Orduna-Malea, E., Martín-Martín, A., & Ayllón, J. M. (2017). Google Scholar: The big data bibliographic tool. In F. J. Cantú-Ortiz (Ed.), *Research Analytics* (1st ed., pp. 59–80). Auerbach Publications. doi: [10.1201/9781315155890-4](https://doi.org/10.1201/9781315155890-4)
- Martín-Martín, A., Costas, R., van Leeuwen, T., & Delgado López-Cózar, E. (2018). Evidence of open access of scientific publications in Google Scholar: A large-scale analysis. *Journal of Informetrics*, 12(3), 819–841. doi: [10.1016/j.joi.2018.06.012](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2018.06.012)
- Wu, M., & Chen, S. (2014). Graduate students appreciate Google Scholar, but still find use for libraries. *The Electronic Library*, 32(3), Article 3. doi: [10.1108/EL-08-2012-0102](https://doi.org/10.1108/EL-08-2012-0102)

Coverage and the Google Scholar database

- Delgado López-Cózar, E., Orduña-Malea, E., & Martín-Martín, A. (2019). Google Scholar as a data source for research assessment. In W. Glänzel, H. F. Moed, U. Schmoch, & M. Thelwall (Eds.), *Springer Handbook of Science and Technology Indicators* (pp. 95–127). Springer International Publishing. doi: [10.1007/978-3-030-02511-3_4](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-02511-3_4)
- Gusenbauer, M. (2019). Google Scholar to overshadow them all? Comparing the sizes of 12 academic search engines and bibliographic databases. *Scientometrics*, 118(1), Article 1. doi: [10.1007/s11192-018-2958-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-018-2958-5)
- Harzing, A.-W., & Alakangas, S. (2016). Google Scholar, Scopus and the Web of Science: A longitudinal and cross-disciplinary comparison. *Scientometrics*, 106(2), Article 2. doi: [10.1007/s11192-015-1798-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-015-1798-9)
- Jensenius, F. R., Htun, M., Samuels, D. J., Singer, D. A., Lawrence, A., & Chwe, M. (2018). The benefits and pitfalls of Google Scholar. *PS: Political Science & Politics*, 51(4), Article 4. doi: [10.1017/S104909651800094X](https://doi.org/10.1017/S104909651800094X)
- Jacso, P. (2008). Testing the calculation of a realistic h-index in Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science for F. W. Lancaster. *Library Trends*, 56(4), Article 4. doi: [10.1353/lib.0.0011](https://doi.org/10.1353/lib.0.0011)
- Majeed, F., Shafiq, M., Ali, A., Awais Hassan, M., Abbas, S. A., Alzahrani, M. E., Saleem, M. Q., Liaqat, H. B., Gardezi, A., & Irshad, A. (2019). Self-citation analysis on Google Scholar dataset for h-Index corrections. *IEEE Access*, 7, 126025–126036. doi: [10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2938657](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2938657)
- Martín-Martín, A., Thelwall, M., Orduña-Malea, E., & Delgado López-Cózar, E. (2021). Google Scholar, Microsoft Academic, Scopus, Dimensions, Web of Science, and OpenCitations' COCI: A multidisciplinary comparison of coverage via citations. *Scientometrics*, 126(1), Article 1. doi: [10.1007/s11192-020-03690-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03690-4)
- Moed, H. F., Bar-Ilan, J., & Halevi, G. (2016). A new methodology for comparing Google Scholar and Scopus. *Journal of Informetrics*, 10(2), Article 2. doi: [10.1016/j.joi.2016.04.017](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2016.04.017)
- Ortega, J. L. (2015). How is an academic social site populated? A demographic study of Google Scholar Citations population. *Scientometrics*, 104(1), 1–18. doi: [10.1007/s11192-015-1593-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-015-1593-7)
- Prins, A. A. M., Costas, R., van Leeuwen, T. N., & Wouters, P. F. (2016). Using Google Scholar in research evaluation of humanities and social science programs: A comparison with Web of Science data. *Research Evaluation*, 25(3), Article 3. doi: [10.1093/reseval/rvv049](https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvv049)
- Rodgers, S., & Zhang, W. (2022). Evaluating reliability of Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science: A study of faculty in U.S. advertising and public relations programs. *Journalism & Mass Communication Educator*, 77(3), 292–307. doi: [10.1177/10776958211064687](https://doi.org/10.1177/10776958211064687)
- van Aalst, J. (2010). Using Google Scholar to estimate the impact of journal articles in Education. *Educational Researcher*, 39(5), Article 5. doi: [10.3102/0013189X10371120](https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X10371120)
- Walters, W. H. (2017). Citation-based journal rankings: Key questions, metrics, and data sources. *IEEE Access*, 5, 22036–22053. doi: [10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2761400](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2761400)

Suggested improvements

- Kearl, M., Noteboom, C., & Tech, D. (2017). A novel improvement to Google Scholar ranking algorithms through broad topic search. *MWAIS 2017 Proceedings*. <https://aisel.aisnet.org/mwais2017/47>
- Thirumaran, S., & Nagarajan, R. (2021). Split and rule algorithm for documents clustering in big data of research articles on Google scholar. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 1070(1), Article 1. doi: [10.1088/1757-899X/1070/1/012068](https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/1070/1/012068)